

16 - Corrective feedback in face-to-face and synchronous computer-mediated communication grammar instruction

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Abstract

This study investigated teachers' practices and perceptions of verbal corrective feedback (CF) in teaching grammar in synchronous computer-assisted communication (SCMC) and face-to-face communication (FTF) contexts for intermediate L2 Chinese learners. The classroom instructional data are based on audio recordings of teacher-student interactions during grammar instruction on simple and complex tasks, CF interventions, pre-tests and post-tests, and instances of CF from teachers' stimulated recall interviews. Three experienced teachers and 36 learners with multilingual background participated in the study. The results showed that oral recast was most frequently used to facilitate Chinese learners' modified output in both FTF and SCMC contexts, while explicit CF was used the least in grammar instruction in the SCMC context. In addition, verbal CF that provided visual support and contextual examples frequently triggered learners' uptake on complex tasks in the grammar instruction. Teachers' perceptions of CF in FTF and SCMC L2 Chinese grammar instruction indicated that confirmed verbal CF provided more than they estimated, and that the CF interaction process was subject to an integrated repertoire across oral, visual, and contextual modalities.

Keywords: Corrective Feedback (CF), Face-to-Face (FTF), Synchronous Computer-Mediated Communication (SCMC), Grammar Instruction, Learner Uptake.

1. Introduction

This study investigates how more explicit and more implicit prompts, also types of interactional corrective feedback (CF), can enhance grammar accuracy of L2 Chinese learners in face-to-face communication (FTF) and synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) context, presents an original study of feedback modalities and task complexity in online and Face-to-Modalities such as synchronous or asynchronous online instruction have different cognitive loads on students (Payne, 2020), students' age, motivation, and learning strategies affect the effectiveness of online instruction (Cooperman, 2018), and students' tasks also have an impact on oral skills and writing ability of second language (L2) learners (Abrams and Byrd, 2016). Although research on various modalities of communication in online teaching and learning has shown different outcomes (Hampel & Stickler, 2012; Liu & Chao, 2018), it has been suggested that the modalities of communication in online interaction should be considered as the most influential and effective in teaching and learning L2 Chinese. However, most of the research focuses on comparing learning outcomes or on specific online teaching techniques, and so far, there is not enough research or discussion related to the gains and feedback in online teaching to address the communication and practices faced by Chinese as a second language (CSL) teachers and learners.

In terms of the implementation of a meaningful modality in L2 Chinese classrooms, teaching L2 Chinese in a virtual environment should be based on the issues and teaching practices that are of substantial concern. Online teaching interaction modalities and collaborative teaching tasks are issues of concern in the field of L2 Chinese teaching and learning, providing the language teaching community with concerned actions in the context of the epidemic, presenting research-based methodologies, addressing pressing issues faced by L2 Chinese teachers and learners, and providing meaningful research and teaching resources. Thus far, in the field of research on teaching L2 Chinese,

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there is limited understanding of the interaction patterns in online and FTF Chinese classrooms, not to mention the effectiveness of the teaching tasks, the benefits of the language input provided by the L2 Chinese teachers, the acquisition of linguistic competence by the L2 Chinese learners in the online teaching and learning environments, as well as the complexity of the tasks of the online and FTF classrooms. The project aims to examine the correlation between feedback modalities, task complexity, and the effectiveness of beginning and intermediate-level instruction in online and FTF L2 Chinese classrooms.

Corrective feedback (CF) on collaborative tasks in L2 Chinese classrooms has been less studied, not to mention face-to-face (FTF) and online input in interactive classroom contexts. The frequency and resolution of language-related episodes (LREs) (Swain & Lapkin, 2000) in synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) and modified output from the learners correcting the language use remain unexplored in the L2 Chinese context. This research project investigates the effect of interactional corrective feedback in face-to-face and online modalities on the pronunciation and grammar gains of L2 Chinese learners. On the other hand, the project also investigates how task complexity affect collaborative oral tasks in the synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) context. Storch (2002) identified four peer interaction patterns in L2 writing work, including collaborative, expert/novice, dominant/dominant, and dominant/passive, based on different degrees of equality and mutuality, and found that L2 learners in pairs exhibited a collaborative stance and produced better texts. Previous studies (Sato and Ballinger, 2016; Li and Zhu, 2017) also verified that tasks play an essential role in web-based L2 collaborative writing. Thus far, studies on collaboration patterns have focused on the effects of different types of tasks on writing rather than different complexity levels of tasks and oral tasks. Previous studies have also demonstrated that learner collaboration facilitates L2 acquisition (Storch, 2011; Sato, 2016; Sato & Viveros, 2016). However, there is still a relative lack of research on the effects of task complexity and corrective feedback on group collaboration of L2 Chinese learners in SCMC interaction. The study also discusses pedagogical implications based on corrective feedback and task complexity in L2 Chinese oral interactions. The present study fills this gap and identifies patterns of teachers' practices and perceptions of verbal corrective feedback (CF) in teaching grammar interaction in collaborative tasks in the SCMC context.

2. Conceptual framework

Corrective feedback (CF) is defined as 'responses to learner utterances containing an error' (Ellis, 2006: 28). It refers to the responses to a learner's errors or non-target-like second language (L2) production. CF feedback has generally been found to be beneficial to second language acquisition (Gass, 1997; Gass & Selinker, 2001; Gass, 2003; Li, 2010), and the "feedback" to be investigated in this research project mainly involves input from teachers in both online (SCMC) and physical (FTF) classrooms. In the early stages, the project focuses on oral recasts, one of the most exerted CF in beginner classrooms (Chen, 2020) and recasts with other visual inputs, and then adjust whether other types of CF should be included to integrate with written (cf. Chen, 2021), multimodal, or contextual inputs after the investigation of the significant types of feedback in both the SCMC and FTF L2 Chinese classrooms. CF modalities, online or physical, synchronous or asynchronous interaction and feedback can affect the effectiveness of L2 Chinese. According to Payne's (2020) categorization of the cognitive load continuum of online learning activity tasks, learners' cognitive load is heaviest when performing online synchronous oral chats, and lightest when performing non-synchronous online discussion or long-term writing tasks. Therefore, while L2 Chinese teachers continue to experiment with tasks of different cognitive complexity, they should also adjust the sequencing of online and physical classroom speaking and writing tasks and CF provision to ensure language development (Robinson, 2011).

Corrective feedback (CF) has been an essential practice in second language classrooms. Teachers used six different feedback moves: recasts, elicitation, clarification requests, metalinguistic feedback, explicit correction, and repetition of error; recasts were the most widely used technique (Lyster & Ranta, 1997). Oral CF moves that withhold correct forms in response to students' errors were categorized into prompts (Lyster & Saito 2010). Prompts were more significant than recasts for increasing accuracy of regular past tense forms, whereas prompts and recasts had similar effects on

improving irregular past tense forms (Yang & Lyster, 2010). Some researchers argue that recasts are the most effective type of corrective feedback in facilitating L2 learning (Long, 2007). Yet, other researchers claim that CF types that withhold the correct form are most likely to contribute to development by pushing learners to stretch their interlanguages (Ammar & Spada, 2006; Lyster, 2004). Recast is a well-formed reformulation of a learner's non-target utterance (Lyster & Ranta, 1997) and has been found to occur most frequently in classroom contexts (Lyster et al., 2013). Additionally, teacher-student and learner-learner interactions have been believed to be beneficial to language development (Philp, Adams, & Iwashita, 2014; Sato & Ballinger, 2016). Recent studies carried out further investigation on the levels of L2 proficiency and paired task performance (Basterrechea & Gallardo-del-Puerto, 2020; Storch & Aldosari, 2013). Timely interactional feedback is an essential component in the virtual environment concerning L2 learning. Oliver and Mackey (2003) reported that their classroom learners noticed recasts to a greater extent in an explicit language lesson than in contexts that involved conversational interaction. Explicit corrective feedback or elicitations are most likely to contribute to development (Lyster, 2004). It is unknown as to if face-to-face (FTF) CF is more beneficial to the pronunciation tasks in pronunciation tasks of L2 Chinese learners than online CF.

Recasts, defined as the reformulation of a learner's utterance, have been argued to be the most effective type of CF in facilitating learning (Long, 2007). Additional or alternative explicit CF practices include a metalinguistic explanation with the provision of rules and examples. Studies have shown that recasts are the most frequently occurring oral CF type in language classrooms (Sheen, 2004; Ellis, 2001; Panova & Lyster, 2002). Grammar instruction has been a critical issue in second language acquisition (SLA), and its practice and effectiveness are related to the development of L2 learners' communicative competence. The development of L2 learners' communicative competence is supported by Sociocultural Theory (SCT), and the classroom language helps teachers transform their thoughts into artifacts (Vygotsky, 1986, 1987) and being the most prominent in the learning activity. Accordingly, the use of language by teachers in grammar instruction should reflect abundant "comprehensible input" (Larsen-Freeman, 2015) to optimize L2 learning. In terms of teaching practices, oral corrective feedback (CF) has been recognized as an instructional strategy and language use that motivates language teachers to communicate with students (Long, 2015; Lyster, 2015), as well as to identify specific skills for accessible input. Although technology-assisted language instructional methods have been employed to promote L2 production (Knight et al., 2018) and listening outcomes (Kam et al., 2020), coupled with a growing interest in the instructional use of multimodal resources such as combining images and sounds (Hafner, 2014, 2015), multimodal instruction in Chinese as a second language (L2 Chinese) classrooms has yet to be explored. Against this background, this study examines CF practices and perceptions in multimodal Chinese grammar teaching.

Previous studies have shown that CF affects specific language forms to varying degrees. Explicit and implicit CF can be linked to feedback mechanisms and performance assessment in L2 classrooms. Various feedback strategies have been adapted in teacher-student interactions. Elicitations refer to feedback that does not correctly reformulate the learner's error pushes the learner to reformulate it (Loewen & Philp, 2006; Lyster, 2004; Nassaji, 2007). Elicitation strategies include self-repair, promoting and providing learners with opportunities to test and revise their hypotheses about the target language (Lyster, 2002, 2004; Lyster & Ranta, 1997). Additionally, elicitation also provide opportunities for negotiation through various forms of requests for clarification and correction (Lyster & Ranta, 1997; Lyster, 1998). On the other hand, prompts were more significant than recasts for increasing accuracy of regular past tense forms, whereas prompts and recasts had similar effects on improving irregular past tense forms (Yang & Lyster, 2010). Additionally, interactional feedback, featuring multiple opportunities to confirm, modify, or reject the hypothesis of L2 learners (Ziegler & Mackey, 2017), has been found to have positive effects on learners' vocabulary and grammar (Akiyama & Saito, 2016) by encouraging negotiation, noticing, and the production of modified output. CF has been proven effective in connecting interaction to L2 development for various linguistic features (Lyster & Saito 2010; Lyster, Saito and Sato, 2013; Nassaji 2016). Elements to be explored in this project include oral prompts in task-based language teaching (TBLT), where oral CF moves that withhold correct forms in response to students' errors were categorized into prompts (Lyster & Saito 2010). Existing research suggests that recasts can have a positive effect on second language

acquisition (SLA), as demonstrated by Mackey and Goo (2007). However, Ellis and Sheen (2006) and Long (2007) point out that the effect of recasts varies according to conditional factors. These factors can be categorized into internal and external variables. Internal factors are related to the learners themselves and include age, ability, working memory and development. On the other hand, external factors are environmental or situational factors, including the learning environment, the specific linguistic features targeted and the recast method. In essence, although recasts facilitate learners' language acquisition, their effectiveness is influenced by the complex interplay of learners' own characteristics and contextual factors.

CF modality could affect individual language development. Rassaei (2019) investigated the effects of computer-mediated, text-based and audio-based corrective feedback (CF) and the moderating role of participants' preferred perceptual styles on the development of English as a foreign language (EFL) learners' English article system. Based on the participants' responses, it was also determined whether their preferred perceptual style was reading/writing or listening. During the course of the treatment, subjects in the experimental group completed several written production tasks and received error correction from either asynchronous text or audio CFs depending on their treatment condition. Oral and written task were used in his study to measure learners' progress after completing the treatment tasks. He found that both text-based and audio-based CF were effective in learners' L2 development, while audio-based CF was more effective than text-based CF. In addition, matching the computer-assisted learning model with the learners' perceptual styles can further improve the effectiveness of computer-assisted learning. It remains to be explored whether audio-based and text-based CF have different impacts on L2 learning, specifically, gains and perspectives of L2 learners and teachers in L2 Chinese classrooms, including SCMC and FTF conditions.

3. Method

The data collection was conducted in an intensive L2 Chinese program. The classes were delivered for five hours per week. Three teachers and their 36 students participated in the investigation, and they were divided into three groups, Class A and Class B constituted the experimental group with oral CF, in contrast to Class C in the control group without oral recast in instruction of phonetic pronunciation. In the experimental group, Class A utilized the oral CF and task-based interaction in the phonetic instruction in the FTF modality, whereas the instruction intervention of Class B was conducted in the SCMC modality. The participating teachers were highly experienced, with a mean experience of 10.8 years. The class size was the same, with 12 students per class, and the students were beginner L2 learners of Chinese from linguistically diverse backgrounds. None were heritage learners, and they began learning Mandarin in adulthood. The mean age for the L2 Chinese learners was 26.5 years (ranged 18-36), and they reported no history of hearing impairments or speech disorders at the time of the investigation.

The study evaluated the complexity of the tasks in intermediate-level Chinese language classroom from the analysis of the classroom corpus and observation, especially the comparison of the oral tasks in the SCMC and FTF classrooms, and the assessment of the writing tasks, although some studies have used the time used by the learner as an estimation to measure the complexity of the cognitive tasks (Baralt, 2013). This study utilized time and space factors to complete the tasks, the amount of information, and the teacher's assessment of the complexity of the task in the early stages of the project, as well as identifying the resource-directing factors in both the SCMC and FTF Chinese classrooms, or the resource-dispersal factors. Resource-dispersing factors were identified for both the SCMC and FTF elementary Chinese language classrooms to observe which resource-directing components directed resources such as attention and memory to the necessary target language features for successful task completion, and which resource-dispersing factors increased implementation or procedural requirements.

Classroom data were compiled based on the interaction in intermediate L2 Chinese classrooms. The experiment was conducted to examine the effect of corrective feedback modalities on L2 learners' grammar patterns in task-based instruction classrooms. The content of the curriculum in the classrooms was controlled. L2 Chinese learners in experimental (with face-to-face or SCMC corrective feedback) and control groups (without corrective feedback) completed task-based

production and elicitation over six weeks, and comprehensibility is measured through listener judgments. Tokens of CF were collected from task-based assessments (EIT), and communicative interactions (paired dialogue) in FTF and online L2 Mandarin classrooms. Language instructors' corrective feedback and the L2 learners' output were compared.

Three language instructors exerted corrective feedback moves or refrained from CF during activities from Week 1 to Week 6 in FTF and SCMC L2 Chinese classrooms. In each treatment session, the researcher sat at the back of the classrooms or joined the online class and took detailed notes of classroom activities and the behavior of the participants. Pre-test was conducted in Week 2. In Week 6, the participants were asked to finish a post-test, a questionnaire survey, followed by a brief personal interview. The pretests and posttests consisted of timed elicited imitation test (EIT) and paired dialogue task. Timed EIT and untimed paired dialogue were administered separately as part of the oral assessments required for the course; instructions and samples were given prior to the implementation of the tasks. Elicited imitation test (EITs) have been used to assess different dimensions that demand real-time, integrative oral linguistic skills, and the technique of elicited imitation requires participants to listen and then repeat as precisely as possible. Empirical studies suggest that EITs offer a good estimate of learners' global oral L2 proficiency levels (Cox and Davies, 2012).

Recast, more explicit (metalinguistic feedback + elicitation), and more implicit prompts (elicitation, repetition, clarification request) were provided when learners made errors during the oral collaborative tasks in the SCMC context. Synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) in the language classroom is multimodal by nature. Both teachers and students deployed a variety of semiotic resources to organize their actions in classroom interactions in the investigation. The collected data reflected teacher-student and student-student interaction speech in L2 Chinese classrooms in the online or SCMC modality.

The interaction patterns of the L2 Chinese learners and communicative strategies were coded and analyzed in Storch's (2002) model, with the indices of equality and mutuality. More explicit (metalinguistic feedback + elicitation) and more implicit prompts (elicitation, repetition, clarification request), and no CF (control group) were provided when learners made errors. The collected data reflect teacher-student and student-student interaction speech in L2 Chinese classrooms in the online modality. L2 learners in experimental (with more explicit or more implicit prompt feedback) and control groups (without prompt feedback) completed the tasks over six weeks. Three language instructors exerted more explicit, more implicit prompt moves or refrained from CF during activities from Week 1 to Week 6 in the SCMC L2 Chinese classrooms.

To measure the CF types and the tokens in each classroom and L2 Chinese learners' responses, the CF incidences the teachers provided was examined to confirm the CF provision in each group. Both colloquial and word-by-word translations were used (Chen, 2020), depending on their significance to show the meanings and the target grammatical structures. Interrater reliability among the three coders was 95%. Oral prompt moves with metalinguistic visual or written input were coded and marked as more explicit prompts. The learners received corrective feedback in the form of elicitation or self-repair. The learners who made errors received commands of repetition or self-repair from the instructors, such as *or zài shuō yí cì* 'say that again', and the correct form was not provided. Elicitation is the instructor's strategic pause in the middle of an utterance to elicit a learner's completion. Practices of elicitation were illustrated by use of a partial repetition of the learner's erroneous utterance, asking questions to elicit the learner's reformulation. Such practices rely on the recordings through communicative interactions in L2 Chinese classrooms.

Tokens of CF were collected from task-based assessments (timed EIT and untimed sentence completion, and picture prompt tests), focus-on-form treatments (CF provision), and communicative interactions (paired dialogue). Language instructors' feedback provision and the L2 learners' output were compared, and language socialization of the L2 Chinese learners was assessed. Some studies have suggested metalinguistic information was provided before form-focused instruction (FFI) lessons (Spada, Lightbown, & White, 2005). Other studies have argued that students produce the target structure accurately in FFI tasks for communicative purposes (Swain, 2005). CF moves aimed at students' errors can be utilized in FFI and push students to practice the target feature in communicative and authentic contexts (Lyster, 2007). The assessment consisted of timed elicited

imitation test (EIT), untimed sentence completion, and picture prompts. Timed EIT and untimed grammar tasks were administrated separately as part of the assessments required for the course; instructions and samples were given prior to the implementation of the oral tasks. Both implicit and explicit knowledge of L2 learners were considered in the timed and untimed testing.

Note that the production tokens in the collaborative tasks were collected and rated. The purpose of the rating task was to investigate the effects of prompts on L2 learners' grammar accuracy of L2 Chinese learners' oral tasks. The oral tasks in the pretest and posttest were analyzed in terms of the accuracy rate of the target structures. In the scoring of the testing materials, the numbers of obligatory uses in the students' answers were counted (cf. Chen, 2021). Consequently, the number of correct instances was divided by the number of obligatory uses. In the ratings procedure of collaboration, minor tone or pronunciation errors in the oral responses did not affect the scoring when the production of the target structures was comprehensible. The oral task was correlated significantly with the tests ($r = .86$), and the factor analysis revealed that all testing scores loading on the same factor accounted for 82% of the variance. The relationship between the tasks indicates that the tests measured the same construct.

4. Results and Discussion

In the intermediate-level classrooms, a mixed ANOVA tested for a significant interaction effect ($\alpha = 0.05$) between groups and testing time, followed by calculations of significance testing and effect sizes (Cohen's d). Results showed no statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in the pretest, $p = 0.1$. The ANOVA showed a significant main effect for testing time, $F(2, 82) = 7.12$, $p < 0.001$, eta squared (η^2) = 0.08, indicating a medium effect size ($d = .76$). Table 1 summarizes the gains of SCMC CF on the grammar tasks.

Table 1 - Summary of CF in the SCMC context

CF Types	Pretest (Time 1)		Posttest (Time 2)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
FTF Recast	0.53	0.14	0.88	0.02
SCMC Recast	0.51	0.11	0.83	0.05
Control Group	0.52	0.12	0.76	0.03

In the FTF condition, pairs with more explicit prompts had significantly higher accuracy rate than the group with more implicit prompts and the control group. Additionally, form-focused instruction with illustrations of concrete grammatical structures and metalinguistic feedback with online visual assets are proven effective. Explicit and implicit prompts affected the collaboration stances in learners' oral tasks regardless of the task complexity. Specifically, intensive form-focused instruction allows L2 learners of Chinese to compare their errors with the target forms and identify features of grammatical structures and increases the accuracy in paired oral interaction.

Findings in this study contribute to our understanding of the CF input and TBLT with group collaboration tasks. The findings verified the effectiveness of interactional prompts on the grammatical gains of beginner L2 learners in the SCMC classroom. Oral prompts were effective when used with other visual assets and written CF in SCMC interaction on the grammar instruction and collaborative tasks. When language learners actively participate in authentic and intentional classroom activities, and visual cues provide constructive feedback, the classroom discourse itself is the meaningful learning. Integration of visual cues (metalinguistic knowledge of the target grammatical structure) can bridge the gaps in classroom communication among the L2 learners in the SCMC context. Interactional prompts can enhance learners' awareness of their errors and the target grammatical structures, and the appropriate application in their grammar tasks, regardless of their linguistic backgrounds.

It is also noteworthy that L2 learners receiving more explicit prompts in form-focused instruction outperformed those without prompts in terms of grammatical gains. Evidently, modalities of corrective feedback, classroom interactions, and the task design could be relevant to the grammar

accuracy and the uptake of L2 learners in beginner Chinese classrooms. Interactional prompts have positive effects on learners' grammar accuracy in beginner L2 Chinese classrooms, and classroom (teacher-student and student-student) interactions, in both FTF created opportunities for language socialization of L2 learners of Mandarin Chinese. L2 learners made errors in the process of language learning, and findings suggest that instructors' CF provision in grammar instruction facilitating L2 grammar acquisition. L2 learners' performing grammar tasks with metalinguistic feedback could be effective in improving their grammar accuracy, and picture prompt and paired dialogue as part of a focus-on-forms task improved L2 learners' communicative strategies. Additionally, exerting prompts in paired dialogue with picture prompts or visual assets has a link with L2 learners' language socialization in the SCMC context. Prompts with metalinguistic clues created more opportunities for meaning negotiation and classroom socialization in the SCMC context.

The dynamics of CF provision in intermediate classes can be found in the instructional process. To investigate the differences of oral CF moves, a one-way ANOVA was performed. The results showed statistically significant differences in oral CF moves, $F(2, 69) = 103.71, p < 0.01$, indicating that the incidence of recasts, explicit CFs, and prompts differed in the L2 Chinese grammar instruction. The participating teachers most frequently exerted oral recasts to facilitate L2 learners' uptake, and explicit CFs were least utilized. Bonferroni's post-hoc comparison showed significant differences between (a) recasts and explicit CF ($p < 0.01$), and (b) between recasts and prompts ($p < 0.01$). The difference between explicit CF and prompts was not significant. Overall, the participating teachers in the grammar instruction most frequently exerted oral recasts, but some variations between experimental groups in the SCMC context and control groups in the FTF context have been attested in the exertion of oral CF. In the exertion of oral CFs, teachers in the experimental group used fewer oral recasts, higher incidence of explicit CF, and higher incidences of prompts. The CF incidence differences between the experimental and control groups were significant ($p < 0.01$) in Bonferroni's post-hoc comparison, indicating different oral CF exertion patterns along with multimodal resources in the experimental group.

In analyzing the CF variation, Weeks 3–4, Weeks 5–6, and Weeks 7–8 were identified as Stage 1, Stage 2, and Stage 3, respectively, and the directional complement (DC) and resultative complement (RC) target structures were instructed in all the stages. The experimental group teachers used higher incidences of prompts (26% in Stage 1, 25% in Stage 2, and 31% in Stage 3) than the control group teachers in grammar instruction with multimodal resources accessible to L2 learners. They elaborated that oral CF moves with visual support and contextual exemplification facilitate L2 learners' successful and partial uptake. Additionally, teachers in the control group utilized oral recasts extensively (more than 80% in all stages), and they confirmed the efficacy and affordances of oral recasts within time constraints in their stimulated recall interviews. Table 3 illustrates the summary of teachers' practices of oral CF moves in grammar instruction with equal hours of recordings (20 hours) from each class.

Table 2 - Summary of teachers' oral CF instances and students' uptake in grammar instruction

Groups	Recast Instances		Explicit CF Instances		Prompt Instances	
	n	(%)	nn	(%)	(%)	(%)
Experimental (n=307)	143	(47%)	80	(26%)	84	(27%)
Uptake (Successful and partial incidence)	123	(86%)	63	(79%)	75	(89%)
Control (n=489)	394	(80%)	38	(8%)	57	(12%)
Uptake (Successful and partial incidence)	239	(61%)	21	(55%)	32	(56%)
Total (N=796)	537	(67%)	118	(15%)	141	(18%)

In addition to demonstrating the effectiveness of CF in FTF and SCMC conditions on L2 development, the results showed that CF provision in the FTF condition was significantly more effective than the same type of CF in the SCMC condition in promoting L2 pronunciation

development. This is an important finding of this project because previous research on SCMC L2 learning has usually examined the effects of asynchronous CF effect, and little is known about the CF effects of SCMC L2 Chinese learning. It is recommended that L2 Chinese teachers provide both oral, written, and multimodal CF in addition to FTF language learning opportunities in the classroom. Given the flexibility of CF provision in the SCMC condition in terms of time and place, it is also recommended that L2 Chinese language teachers provide asynchronous and synchronous CF in their classrooms. The findings also provide evidence that teachers should be aware that individual differences in language learners, such as their preferences, may affect their learning outcomes upon receiving CF. Different learners may derive different benefits from different CF modalities in their L2 Chinese learning.

Comparing the types of feedback on grammar instruction, the FTF context provided L2 learners with more opportunities to collaborate in learning to write Chinese characters. For example, when the teacher assigns students to recognize a reading, students will respond directly if they do not know how to read, whereas in FTF contexts, L2 learners tend to ask the classmates next to them or the classmates next to them take the initiative to help. One weakness of the SCMC context relates to pronunciation correction in grammar instruction because students may not always pay attention to the teacher's gestures and facial expressions in the SCMC context. In addition, pronunciation errors in SCMC contextualized grammar instruction classes often involved non-verbal feedback, and all participating teachers agreed that body language such as lip-syncing, hand gestures, head raising, head lowering, and foot stomping would be present in the SCMC classroom. Task-based grammar interactions require resource-directed dimensions such as spatial reasoning and here and now/there elements. The participating teachers were reported to utilize orientation words such as "in front, behind, above, below, etc. to help students memorize the movements similar to the Chinese character shapes in both FTF and SCMC condition, along with verbal CF.

It should be noted that verbal modeling and visual aids are equally important in teaching L2 Chinese grammar. In addition to modeling and instruction of grammatical structures, it is necessary to explain the sequence and gradually approach the requirements of the target task in two dimensions: resource-directing and dispersing. Increasing task complexity does not increase the output of complex structures when students are not focused at that time. Intermediate-level learners were usually able to correct errors after the teachers provided CF. When repeated errors occurred, the teachers supplemented the verbal CF with visual aids. Of particular interest is the interaction of differences in attitudes and engagement of Chinese second language learners in completing the task, which affected their grammatical accuracy. The most significant difference in the performance of L2 Chinese learners in the FTF and SCMC conditions was the level of engagement, which is a challenge for all participating teachers involved in an online classroom, where they must keep track of the level of student engagement. Additionally, the degree of completeness in "oral expression" varied. Oral recasts in FTF condition on complex tasks seemed worked better compared to simpler tasks in such group collaboration. In SCMC classrooms, gains in L2 Chinese learners' grammatical accuracy were associated with interactive and prompt CF provision. Form-focused instruction through illustrations of grammatical structures and metalinguistic feedback through FTF and SCMC visual assets proved effective.

5. Conclusion

This study investigates how more explicit and more implicit prompts, also types of interactional corrective feedback, can enhance grammar accuracy of L2 Chinese learners in synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) context. Pretests and posttests were conducted to examine the effect of more explicit and more implicit prompts on L2 learners' grammatical gains in classrooms with learners from different linguistic backgrounds. The findings verified the effectiveness of interactional prompts on the grammatical gains of beginner and intermediate-level L2 learners in the SCMC classroom. The group with more explicit prompts had significantly higher accuracy rate than the group with more implicit prompts and the control group, and groups with more implicit prompts in the SCMC classroom outperformed the control group. Evidently, form-focused instruction with illustrations of concrete grammatical structures and metalinguistic feedback with online visual

assets are proven effective. Interactional prompts can enhance L2 Chinese learners' awareness of their errors and the target grammatical structures, and the appropriate application in their grammar tasks, regardless of their linguistic backgrounds. Modalities of corrective feedback, classroom interactions, and the task design could be relevant to the grammar accuracy and the uptake of L2 learners in Chinese classrooms. Classroom interactions, including teacher-student and student-student interactions, created opportunities for language socialization of L2 learners of Mandarin Chinese. Exerting prompts in paired dialogue with picture prompts or visual assets has a link with L2 learners' language socialization in the SCMC context.

It can be seen that L2 learners made errors during the language learning process and the CF provided by the participating teachers during grammar instruction facilitated the acquisition of L2 Chinese grammar. L2 learners' collaborative tasks with metalinguistic feedback could be effective in improving their grammar accuracy, and picture prompt and paired dialogue as part of a focus-on-forms task improved their communicative strategies. Prompts with metalinguistic clues created more opportunities for classroom socialization and learning in progress in the SCMC condition. In summary, the effectiveness of more explicit and more explicit prompts in the SCMC classroom was verified, and more explicit prompts in the SCMC classroom outperformed the control group. These findings shed light on prompt feedback and grammar instruction in beginner L2 Chinese classrooms. It is noteworthy that grammatical gains of L2 learners could be associated with modalities of prompts, target grammatical structures, and the design of the grammar tasks in the SCMC context.

Additionally, intensive form-focused grammar instruction allows L2 learners of Chinese to compare their errors with the target forms and identify features of grammatical structures and increases the accuracy in paired oral interaction. It can be seen that increased task complexity did not affect in classroom interaction patterns and grammar accuracy, suggesting that manipulating task complexity might not work for L2 Chinese learners' interactions. CF treatments, on the other hand, affected the grammar and pronunciation accuracy in both FTF and SCMC. L2 Chinese learners' perception of CF may have affected their I group interaction. Additionally, forms and functions produced by L2 Chinese learners during CF treatment contributed to the collaborative stances of paired dialogue in the SCMC context. The interactive demands and peer feedback in collaborative tasks may have moderated the effect of task complexity in the oral and grammar tasks.

The results showed that oral recast was most frequently used to facilitate Chinese learners' modified output in both FTF and SCMC contexts, while explicit CF was used the least in grammar instruction in the SCMC context. In addition, verbal CF that provided visual support and contextual examples frequently triggered learners' uptake on complex tasks in the grammar instruction. Teachers' perceptions of CF in FTF and SCMC L2 Chinese grammar instruction indicated that confirmed verbal CF provided more than they estimated, and that the CF interaction process was subject to an integrated repertoire across oral, visual, and contextual modalities. Findings in this study contribute to our understanding of the corrective feedback input, engagement in negotiations for meaning in L2 Chinese learning, task complexity and group collaboration. The study sheds light on the dynamics of oral tasks and pedagogical implications for L2 Chinese teaching and learning. In particular, well-designed tasks in FTF and SCMC classrooms may induce L2 Chinese learners to enhance monitoring behaviors, to engage in more in-depth collaboration with language learning, and to increase opportunities for interactive language learning. L2 Chinese teachers can increase learners' attention to form-meaning mapping in task-based planning by designing and sequencing instructional tasks, with adequate CF provision in both FTF and SCMC classrooms.

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